

Tiakina Wāhine Hapū

Nurture Women in Pregnancy

Finding a way to respectfully
Discuss
Smoking During
Pregnancy,
can be difficult.

Dr Marewa Glover's award-winning mini-series *Tiakina Wāhine Hapū* follows a whānau through pregnancy... and shows how much easier it would be to make changes for pēpi if all the whānau experienced being pregnant.

Check out the YouTube Series
and download your **FREE** copy at
www.corieess.com

“When one of us is pregnant, all of us are pregnant.”

That is the message of this humorous look at pregnancy, whānau support, and some of the changes pregnant women make to protect the health of their pēpi.

He pēpi,
He rangatira.

This award winning series by Dr Marewa Glover Ph.D. won Best Picture & Best Director at the 2019 GFN Film Festival.

